

Biligand Complexes of Some Lanthanides with Multidentate Chelones and Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic Acid

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1 : 1 : 1 M(III)-CDTA/DTPA-PDA ternary systems have been investigated potentiometrically [M(III)=La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III); CDTA=1,2-diaminocyclohexane-tetraacetic acid, DTPA=diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid, PDA=pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid]. The formation constants ($\log K_{M,L,L'}$) of the mixed ligand complexes formed through the simultaneous coordination of both the ligands have been evaluated at constant temperature $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M KNO_3$). The relative order of stabilities is observed as $La < Pr < Nd$ and $CDTA < DTPA$.

In recent years interesting complexes of metals of unusual coordination numbers¹⁻⁴, polycentric⁵, hydroxo⁶ and protonated⁷⁻⁹ nature have been reported. Hoard *et al*¹⁰ made X-ray studies of the complex [Ln-EDTA.4H₂O] and reported ten coordination number for lanthanide ions. To observe a further expansion in coordination number of lanthanide ions we have studied 1 : 1 : 1, M(III)-CDTA/DTPA-PDA complexes in which the metal ions appear to attain their coordination number eleven.

Experimental

Solutions of metal nitrates, tri- and tetrapotassium salts of CDTA and DTPA, respectively, KNO₃ and KOH (A.R., B.D.H. or Fluka) were prepared in double distilled water and standardised as described earlier^{1,3,11}. The solution of PDA was prepared by direct weighing. Philips pH-meter (PR 9405) was used for the potentiometric titrations at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ as mentioned earlier^{1,3}.

Results and Discussion

Identical titration curves were obtained for the corresponding systems of all the metals studied. Hence only the curves for the systems 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA/DTPA-PDA have been discussed to show the mode of formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary species in general.

Curve a (Fig. 1) represents the titration of metal nitrate showing basic salt formation¹¹. Two inflections at $m=1$ and $m=2$ on the curve b (Figs. 1 and 2) indicate the titration of two carboxylic protons of PDA in two distinct steps.

Binary systems :

The formation of 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA/DTPA complex^{1,3} is shown by the curve c (Figs. 1 and 2), respectively. A well-defined inflection on the curve d at $m=2$ (Figs. 1 and 2) is attributed to the formation of 1 : 1 La(III)-PDA binary complex in low pH

Fig. 1. La(III)-CDTA-PDA.

Fig. 2. La(III)-DTPA-PDA.

- | | | | |
|----|------------------------------|----|------------------------------|
| a | La(III)-Nitrate | b | PDA |
| b | PDA | b' | K ₄ DTPA |
| b' | K ₄ CDTA | c | 1 : 1 ; La(III)-DTPA |
| c | 1 : 1 ; La(III)-CDTA | d | 1 : 1 ; La(III)-PDA |
| d | 1 : 1 ; La(III)-PDA | e | 1 : 1 : 1 ; La(III)-DTPA-PDA |
| e | 1 : 1 : 1 ; La(III)-CDTA-PDA | T | Theoretical composite curve |
| T | Theoretical composite curve | → | Appearance of ppt |
| → | Appearance of ppt | | |

as evidenced by initial lowering in pH of this curve as compared to curve b.

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Ternary systems :

Curve e (Figs. 1 and 2) shows the pH titration of 1 : 1 : 1 La(III)-CDTA/DTPA-PDA ternary system. A lowering in pH of this curve as compared to that of the curves representing the binary systems (curves c and d) and a single well-defined inflection at m=3 may be attributed to the simultaneous addition of both the ligands to the metal ion forming 1 : 1 : 1 bi-ligand soluble species.

The formation of the above ternary species is further supported by the absence of any solid phase during the titration and also the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve^{1,2} T.

In the above ternary species the metal ions appear to attain an expanded coordination number provided the nitrogen atoms of CDTA, DTPA and PDA remain coordinated to the metal ions. These complexes bear the following (a and b) structures of expanded coordination numbers.

Calculations :

The acid dissociation constant of the ligands PDA ($pK_1 = 2.57$; $pK_2 = 4.33$), K_3 CDTA ($pK = 11.10$) and K_4 DTPA ($pK = 10.10$) were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell^{1,3}.

For 1 : 1 : 1 MLL' species (where L=monobasic acid and L'=dibasic acid), the reaction and equilibrium constant are

If T_M , T_L and $T_{L'}$ are the total concentrations of metal ion, ligand HL and the ligand H_2L , respectively, then

$$T_M = [M] + [MLL'] \quad \dots (2)$$

$$T_L = [HL] + [L] + [MLL'] \quad \dots (3)$$

$$T_{L'} = [H_2L'] + [HL'] + [L'] + [MLL'] \quad \dots (4)$$

The concentrations of other possible species like hydroxo or polynuclear ones are negligible in lower pH range where equilibrium studies are made and hence have not been taken into consideration. Charges have also been omitted for the sake of clarity. The dissociation constants of the ligands

$$HL \text{ is } K = \frac{[H][L]}{[HL]} \quad \dots (5a)$$

and of the ligand H_2L' is $K_1 = \frac{[HL'][H]}{[H_2L']}$ and

$$K_2 = \frac{[L'][H]}{K_2} \text{ or } K_1 K_2 = \frac{[H]^2 [L']}{[H_2L']} \quad \dots (5b)$$

Now combining eqs. 3 and 4 and introducing the dissociation constant from eqs. 5a and 5b.

$$T_L + T_{L'} = [HL] + [L] + [H_2L'] + [HL'] + [L'] + 2[MLL'] \text{ or } [MLL'] = T_M - 1/2\{[L]x + [L']y\}$$

($\because T_M = T_L = T_{L'}$) ... (6)

$$(x = \frac{[H]}{K} + 1 \text{ and } y = \frac{[H]^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{[H]}{K_2} + 1)$$

On substituting the value of [MLL'] from eq. 6 into eq. 3 we get

$$[M] = 1/2\{[L]x + [L']y\} \quad \dots (7)$$

since during simultaneous chelation of both the ligands to the metal ion the total hydrogen ions liberated are supposed to be neutralised simultaneously by the base used. Here, below 'a' are the moles of bases added per mole of metal ion or HL or H_2L' and will be shared simultaneously by monobasic HL, as well as by dibasic H_2L' , owing to their respective 1/3rd and 2/3rd contribution to the total hydrogen ion concentration present in equilibrium. Thus the other pertinent equations are :

$$1/3\{aT_L + [H] - [OH]\} = [L] + [MLL'] \quad \dots (8a)$$

$$\text{and } 2/3\{aT_{L'} + [H] - [OH]\} = [HL] + 2[L'] + 2[MLL'] \quad \dots (8b)$$

Substituting the value of [MLL'] from equation 3 in equation 8a we get

$$T_L - 1/3\{aT_L + [H] - [OH]\} = \frac{[L][H]}{K}$$

$$(HL = \frac{[H][L]}{K} \text{ vide eq. 5a})$$

$$\text{or } [L] = \frac{T_L - 1/3\{aT_L + [H] - [OH]\}}{[H]/K} \quad \dots (9a)$$

$$\text{Similarly, } [L'] = \frac{2T_{L'} - 2/3\{aT_{L'} + [H] - [OH]\}}{\frac{2[H]^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{[H]}{K_2}} \quad \dots (9b)$$

Now on putting the values of $[MLL']$, $[M]$, $[L]$ and $[L']$ from eq. nos. 6, 7, 9a and 9b, respectively into the eq. 1, we get the value of $K_{MLL'}$ as

$$K_{MLL'} = \frac{T_M - 1/2\{[L]x + [L']y\}}{1/2\{[L]x + [L']y\} \cdot [L] \cdot [L']} \quad \dots (10)$$

Formation constants ($\log K_{MLL'}$) of the complexes at $25 \pm 1^\circ$:

The calculated values of $\log K_{MLL'}$ are recorded in Table 1. The relative order of stability in terms

TABLE 1		
System	$\log K_{MLL'}$	ΔG° kcal/degree/mole
La(III)-CDTA-PDA	11.67 ± 0.16	-15.90
Pr(III)-CDTA-PDA	11.75 ± 0.10	-16.01
Nd(III)-CDTA-PDA	11.90 ± 0.12	-16.21
La(III)-DTPA-PDA	12.63 ± 0.10	-17.21
Pr(III)-DTPA-PDA	12.75 ± 0.08	-17.37
Nd(III)-DTPA-PDA	12.85 ± 0.14	-17.51

of metal ions is $La < Pr < Nd$ and may be explained on the basis of decreasing size and increasing ionic potential (charge/radius) of lanthanide ions. The enhanced stability of the complexes involving octadentate DTPA as compared to that of hexadentate CDTA complexes may be attributed to the increased number of fused rings and this gives a further evidence of metal ions being coordinated with both the ligands through their nitrogen atom resulting in the formation of complex species of unusual coordination number.

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